

Management of Support Services and Quality Service Delivery Among Academic Staff in the University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined management support services and quality service delivery among academic staff of the University of Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the aim of this study, two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the academic staff in the University of Calabar. The total number of all the academic staff is three thousand eight hundred and sixty (3860). A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a total number of one hundred (100) respondents. Primary data for the study were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled "Management Support Service and Quality Service Delivery among Academic Staff Questionnaire (MSSQSDQ). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by psychometric and higher education experts all in the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 25 was used for data analysis. Findings showed that there is no significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery; there is no significant relationship between management of infrastructural support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. It was recommended that the management of the university should make provision for staff support service as well infrastructural support service specifically in terms of office spaces and the provision of a public address system for easy and effective communication in the lecture halls.

Keywords: Academic staff, quality, service delivery, services, support services

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Introduction

Management is an essential tool used by the university to enhance quality service delivery because it involves getting things done through others. This requires the harnessing of all the resources of an organisation towards the achievement of the goals of the organisation. It also involves the guidance or direction of the people and materials towards the achievement of organisational goals (Mbipom, 2000). Unachukwu and Okoji (2014) posit that management is

both an art and science because it involves getting work done with the help of people using their available resources within a given time limit. For management to be effective, there are certain activities or functions required for the successful completion of a process, program or project called support services. These support services are often managed by a separate department and it is extremely vital that every university should have an effective management support service to succeed in the business of teaching, research and community service.

Management support services, according to Unachukwu and Okorji (2014), is the process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts and resources that individuals and school organizations need to survive in a dynamic environment. It is therefore pertinent to note that the kind and level of support services rendered to the academic staff of the university can go a long way in impacting positively, the quality of their service delivery. Some of the support services that could be managed to enhance quality service delivery in the university have not been adequately utilized (Owan, 2018). Lewis and Booms in Wonah (2017) view service quality delivery as a way or measure in which service level is being satisfactorily delivered by the members of the academic staff matches with the students and university management expectations. From the above, quality service is the maintaining of standards that meet or exceed the students and university management's expectations. Quality Service has been seen as an assessment of how well lecturers delivered services to their students. Swearingen (2012) asserted that quality service is an extra activity rendered by the academic staff to his or her students in the university and the production and consumption of such services usually have a specific duration and time frame that each student is expected to complete. Palmer (2005) opined that quality service involves the provision of goods/ services by the academic staff to his or her students in the university based on the specification that satisfies the requirement of the university management.

Staff support services are the various development programmes provided by the school board and implemented by the university management to enhance quality service delivery. They refer to the formal processes of improving the capabilities of teaching staff by way of providing lecturer professional training and developmental opportunities. Student success and satisfaction is directly linked to their engagement with academic staff therefore the university has a significant role to play in ensuring that their staff have the necessary training and information needed to enhance their duties. Educational infrastructural support services are provided by the school board and maintained by the school principal. They involve the provision and maintenance of supportive physical, moral and social development of the learners during curricular co-curricular activities. Participation in such activities results in acquiring great values including self-discipline, moderation, brotherhood, true democracy, co-operation, good physique and higher academic achievement.

Osagie (2016) examined the relationship between staff development programmes and their productivity in secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria. The design of the study was a descriptive survey, while a random sampling technique was used to get a sample of 125 respondents from a population of 250 principals. An instrument titled: Teacher Development Programmes and Productivity Scale (TDPPS) was used for data collection. Pearson product-

moment correlation was used for data analysis. Findings revealed a strong correlation between teachers' development programmes such as instructional supervision, in-service training and co-teaching, and their productivity in terms of motivation, high teacher performance and high students' success rate.

Eze (2016) study the impact of training and retraining on teachers' productivity in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design. A20-item questionnaire was used for data collection. A sample of 256 teachers was used for the study while an independent t-test was used for data analysis. Results showed that training and retraining did enhance teachers' productivity to a great extent. Finding also revealed that the perception of male and female teachers significantly differed on the impact of training and retraining on their productivity.

The study of Owan (2018) assessed the connection between educational support service management and the achievement of Universal Basic Education objectives in Cross River State was studied. The complete population of 2,078 primary school administrators in the state was studied using a census method. The tools utilized to gather data were the "Management of Educational Support Services Questionnaire (MESSQ)" and the "Achievement of Universal Basic Education Goals Questionnaire (AUBEGQ)". The data were examined using descriptive statistics, and all null hypotheses were evaluated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis with a.05 alpha level. The study's findings indicate that management of guidance/counselling services, staff development services, and ICT services are all positively associated with achieving Universal Basic Education objectives. According to these findings, it was suggested that the ministry of education provide sufficient supply of professional guidance counsellors in all primary schools in Cross River State in order to assist students with their psychological and persona-social requirements.

Uko (2015) investigated how the proficiency and creativity of principals in the management of school facilities influence teachers' task performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated for the study. The sample of the study included 36 secondary schools, with two schools randomly drawn from each of the 18 Local Government Areas in the state. The primary data were collected from a questionnaire titled: School Facilities Management Questionnaire (SFMQ) and personal interview, while the secondary data were collected from checklists, school records and documents, journals and the internet. The data were given both qualitative and quantitative treatment. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient statistical instrument was adopted for the analysis. The findings showed that there was a significant relationship between the principals' proficiency, creativity and the overall educational objectives in the management of school facilities. It is against this background that the researcher intends to investigate management support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

In recent years, the researcher's experience and observation seem to show that there is a problem of poor-quality service delivery by some of the academic staff of the university. which may likely be as a result of lack of staff support service as well as lack of infrastructural service. For instance, some academic staff that would have contributed their effort toward enhancing quality service delivery in the university lack staff support services such as instructional supervision and co-teaching, which have affected their productivity in the university. Also, some academic staff lack infrastructural facilities such as conducive offices to effective research and compile notes for lectures and prepare assessments for students; and public address systems to lecture large numbers of students which would enhance quality service delivery in the university. This seems to have manifested in the poor services rendered by some of the academic staff of the university. Although several attempts such as staff development opportunities and provision of infrastructural facilities have been provided by university management, the problem of poor-quality service persists. It is against this backdrop that the researcher intends to examine management support services and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to examine management support services and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to investigate the following:

1. Whether management of staff support services related to quality service delivery among academic staff in the University of Calabar.
2. Whether management of infrastructural service relate to quality service delivery among academic staff in the University of Calabar

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar
2. There is no significant relationship between management of infrastructural service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar

Methods

The study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the academic staff in the University of Calabar. The total number of all the academic staff is three thousand eight hundred and sixty (3860). A stratified random sampling technique was used to select total numbers of one hundred (100) respondents from the University of Calabar. Relevant

data for the study was collected with researchers developed questionnaire titled: "Management Support Services and Quality Service Delivery among Academic Staff Questionnaire (MSSQSDQ). The instrument was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A sought respondents' demographic data such as the name of department, sex, rank, and qualification. Section B consisted of ten (10) items constructed in a four (4) point modified Likert scale ranging from strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in the administration of higher education and measurement and evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 25 was used for data analysis and the results are presented in the respective tables.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. The calculated result is presented in table one. The result in Table 1 revealed that the calculated r-value of .589** was significantly greater than the critical value of 0.423 when tested at the .05 level of significance with 98 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar.

Table 1: Summary of Correlation analysis of the relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff in the University of Calabar (n=100)

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	r cal.	P-value
Staff support service	17.58	2.547	.589**	.000
Quality service delivery in the university	17.16	2.561		

** Significant at .05 level; df = 98 critical –r.423

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between the management of infrastructural service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. The calculated result is presented in table two. The result in table 2 revealed that the calculated r-value of .562** was significantly greater than the critical value of 0.423 when tested at the .05 level of significance with 98 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between

the management of infrastructural support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar.

Table 2: Summary of Correlation analysis of the relationship between management of infrastructural support service and quality service delivery among academic staff in the University of Calabar (n=100)

Variables	Mean	SD	r cal.	P-value
Infrastructural support service	17.36	2.709	.562*	.000
Quality service delivery in the university	17.16	2.561		

** Significant at .05 level; df = 98 critical – r = .423

Discussion

The result of hypothesis one stated that there is a significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. This result is in agreement with the finding of Osagie (2016) whose study revealed a strong correlation between teachers' development programmes such as instructional supervision, in-service training and co-teaching, and their productivity in terms of motivation, high teacher performance and high students' success rate. Also, the study is in agreement with Eze (2016) whose study revealed that the perception of male and female teachers significantly differed on the impact of training and retraining on their productivity.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant relationship between management of infrastructural support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. This result is in agreement with the finding of Uko (2015) whose study investigated how the proficiency and creativity of principals in the management of school facilities influence teachers' task performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings showed that there was a significant relationship between the principals' proficiency, creativity and the overall educational objectives in the management of school facilities.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of data collected, analyzed and the findings derived, the study concluded that there is a significant relationship between management of staff support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar. Finally, the study revealed also that there is a significant relationship between the management of infrastructural support service and quality service delivery among academic staff at the University of Calabar.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it is recommended that the management of the university should make provision for staff support service as well infrastructural support

service specifically in terms of office spaces and the provision of a public address system for easy and effective communication in the lecture halls.

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